

Diphenylcarbazide as a Sensitive Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) in Presence of Pyridine

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Diphenylcarbazide reacts with vanadium(V) in presence of pyridine giving an intense violet coloured complex which is extractable into chloroform. Vanadium is determined spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance of the complex at 530 nm against a reagent blank. Beer's law being obeyed upto 1.6 ppm. The method is free from the interference of large number of elements. The method is quite simple and uses ordinary reagents. It is very sensitive method and has been successfully applied for the analysis of trace levels of vanadium in synthetic samples.

LITERATURE survey reveals that diphenylcarbazide has been widely used as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of chromium in ores¹, sea water², animal tissue digests³ etc. The reagent also finds applications in the determination of other elements, mercury, lead and nickel⁴. Using the same reagent a method is also reported for the determination of vanadium⁵ but it does not meet the requirements of good sensitivity and selectivity. Preliminary investigations revealed that sensitivity of the reaction of vanadium with diphenylcarbazide could be enhanced by the addition of pyridine, thus forming an intense pink-violet coloured complex. The complex is extractable into many solvents but the choice of chloroform as extractant has been found to be more convenient. Accordingly, a highly sensitive method is proposed here for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium after extracting the complex into chloroform.

Only a few spectrophotometric methods are available for the determination of trace amounts of vanadium in samples containing molybdenum as major constituent because molybdenum is found to interfere in many of the existing methods⁶⁻¹⁰. The proposed method, besides other elements, is free from the interference of molybdenum and has been successfully applied in the analysis of such synthetic samples.

Experimental

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of vanadium(V) was prepared from sodium metavanadate and standardised titrimetrically¹¹. The stock solution was further diluted to give a standard solution containing 10 ppm of vanadium. Standard solutions of other elements (1-10 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by

dissolving suitable salts in water, dilute sulphuric or dilute hydrochloric acid. A 2% (w/v) solution of diphenylcarbazide (DPC) was prepared in acetone (B.D.H.). Pyridine (A.R.), chloroform (B.D.H.) and sulphuric acid (1N) were used.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing vanadium ($\leq 40 \mu\text{g}$) taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel, were added diphenylcarbazide solution (1ml), pyridine (2 ml), 1N sulphuric acid (0.4 ml) and enough distilled water to give an aqueous phase volume of 10 ml, and allowed to stand for 30 min. The violet complex was extracted with chloroform (10 ml), shaking for 30 s; the extraction being repeated with chloroform (5 ml). The extracts were combined in a 25 ml standard flask to which anhydrous sodium sulphate was added after making up the volume with chloroform. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 530 nm (Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer) with matched 1 cm glass cells against reagent blank. The amount of vanadium was determined in the sample solution from standard calibration curve.

Samples containing iron, nickel, cobalt, copper and chromium were masked with potassium cyanide.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(V) gives a pink complex with DPC in slightly acidic solution showing maximum absorbance at 545-550 nm. The sensitivity of the reaction is increased many times by the addition of pyridine forming a violet coloured complex. The complex is extractable by chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate, isopentyl acetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl alcohol and n-butanol; extraction decreasing in that

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order. Among these, chloroform is preferred because of maximum absorbance.

The absorbance spectra of the vanadium(v)—pyridine—DPC complex and that of the reagent blank is shown in Fig. 1. The reagent blank exhibits a well defined peak at 305 nm also shown by the complex, but with reduced intensity and slight shift of λ_{max} towards longer wavelength. The complex shows a broad absorption band at 530–535 nm where the blank shows little absorbance.

extraction and 0.5–5 min of equilibration with chloroform.

The complex is quite stable and absorbance of the complex remains unchanged for at least 24 h. The colour system obeying Beer's law for vanadium concentration up to $1.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity $4.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Composition of the complex : The nature of the complex was investigated by Job's method of

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of vanadium(v)-pyridine-diphenylcarbazide complex in chloroform : (A) $0.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V measured against reagent blank, and (B) reagent blank against chloroform.

Effect of variables : The effect of various parameters on the extraction of vanadium(v)—pyridine—DPC complex was studied. In these studies, aqueous phase (10 ml) containing vanadium (3 ppm) was extracted after 5 min of mixing. Addition of pyridine causes synergistic enhancement of colour intensity but the reaction is slow and requires at least 30 min time for full colour development at room temperature. Order of adding the reagents is also important. Addition of DPC and then pyridine to the aqueous phase followed by acid, gives the highest absorbance. The extraction of the complex is influenced by the change in acidity. The extraction of the complex is a little in the absence of sulphuric acid, but it increases with sulphuric acid concentration and becomes maximum in the range 0.4–1.6 ml of 1N sulphuric acid; beyond this range, the extraction decreases. Other optimum conditions for maximum absorbance are 1.0–1.5 ml of 2% DPC solution, 2.0–2.5 ml of pyridine, 30–40 min of waiting time before

continuous variations^{1,2} (Fig. 2) at fixed pyridine concentration. The molar ratio of vanadium to diphenylcarbazide in the complex was found to be 1 : 1.

Interference studies : The effect of foreign ions was studied in the determination of 1.5 ppm of vanadium(v). Simple anions like chloride, sulphate, nitrate and acetate do not interfere. Oxalate, citrate, EDTA, tartrate and ascorbic acid even in traces interfere seriously. Tungsten, lead, zirconium and thorium are not extracted but suppress the extraction of vanadium thus lowering their tolerance limits. The interference of chromium, iron, cobalt, nickel and copper can be prevented by cyanide. The reaction of vanadium in presence of copper and iron is slow thus requires 60 min of waiting time instead of 30 min. The tolerance limits (in μg) of various ions is as follows: cyanide (10000), fluoride (20), phosphate (20), thiourea (100), Ca^{2+} (200), Sr^{2+} (200), Ba^{2+} (200), Mg^{2+} (200), Be^{2+} (200),

As^V (200), Mo^{VI} (200), La^{III} (50), Tl^I (50), Ti^{IV} (1), Pd^{II} (1), Mn^{II} (50), Cd^{II} (50), Ce^{IV} (50), Hg^{II} (10), Ag^I (10), Au^{III} (10), Bi^{III} (5), Sb^{III} (5), Sn^{II} (5), Zr^{IV} (5), Th^{IV} (5), Al^{III} (5), W^{VI} (2), U^{VI} (2), Pb^{II} (2), Cu^{II} (50), Ni^{II} (50), Co^{II} (10), Fe^{III} (3), Cr^{VI} (2).

Fig. 2. Continuous variation of vanadium(v) and diphenylcarbazide: (A) $7.84 \times 10^{-4} M$, and (B) $3.91 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Applications : The proposed method is one of the most sensitive methods available for the determination of trace levels of vanadium. The method is quite simple and utilises easily available reagents.

Besides alkali and alkaline earths, the method is free from the interference of Mo, W, Ti, Zr, Th, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Cr, U, Sn, Sb, As, Bi, Pb, Al, Ag, Hg, Au, Mn, La and Ce. The method should be useful in the analysis of many vanadium containing alloys and other industrial products. Real samples were not available. Therefore, the utility of the method was tested by analysing a few synthetic samples.

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References

1. G. CHUNSAN and F. YUGING, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1981, 9, 414.
2. S. TSUNENBU and G. SHIRO, *Bull. Inst. Chem. Res. Kyoto Univ.*, 1977, 55, 429.
3. W. C. BRYSON and C. M. GOODALL, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1981, 124, 391.
4. I. K. GSEINOV and S. I. BAGBANLY, *Issled Vobl. Neorg. Fiz. Khim.*, 1977, 102.
5. L. P. PANDEY, *Natl. Met. Lab. Tech. J.*, 1977, 19, 45.
6. V. YATIRAJAM and S. P. ARYA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 86, 209.
7. J. JOSEF, *Sb. Ved. Pr. Vys. Sk. Chemickotechnol. Pardubice*, 1971, 25, 23.
8. N. KURMAIAH and V. P. R. RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 367.
9. Z. SKORKO, *Trybula Nukleonika*, 1965, 10, 559.
10. A. SETEU and V. BUZURA, *Stud. Univ. Babes-Bolyei, Ser. Chem.*, 1967, 12, 35.
11. G. CHARLOT and D. BEZIER, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Methuen, London, 1957, p. 623.
12. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.